

IN TEACHING ENGLISH: APPROACH, METHOD, AND TECHNIQUE

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Abstract. *This article emphasizes the need for English teachers to pay attention to three terms that are important for them to know before teaching language skills to schoolchildren, namely: the difference between "approach," "method," and "technique," their systemic interconnection and harmonious interaction, which will serve as a basis for introducing new ideas into educational activities and pedagogical research.*

Keywords: *approach, method, English language, technique, school.*

Introduction

Learning a second language is a long and complex process. When a person begins to learn a second language, they first need a deep command of their native language, and then they strive for a new language, a new culture, a new way of thinking, feeling, and acting; their entire personality and being are involved in the process of language acquisition. Successful language learning requires complete dedication, full participation, and total physical, mental, and emotional commitment. The language learning process involves many factors.

Language learning is not a quick and easy program consisting of a series of simplified steps. Since most of the responsibility falls on the language teacher, language courses and classes are often ineffective if they are not organized in an effective environment. As a result, some language learners may find it difficult to speak a foreign language fluently in a classroom setting.

For the teacher, learning and teaching cannot be viewed as opposing processes. On the contrary, this opposition only partially disappears when he or she views the learning process as a support for teaching. Successful foreign language teaching requires, among other things, a certain understanding of the factors that determine how and why a person succeeds or fails in learning a second language. So where should a teacher begin to understand the principles of language learning and teaching? First of all, they should start by reflecting on questions they can ask themselves: "What should be taught?", "What should the stages be?", "What approach, procedure, methods, techniques, and tools should be used?" Such questions determine the educational perspective, i.e., the goal, content, essence of the lesson, and expected outcome. This process determines the degree to which the teacher achieves acmeological competence.

In this regard, English teachers must correctly understand and apply the difference between three terms when determining the trajectory of their own working style. These terms are "approach," "method," and "technique." If English teachers do not understand the essence of these three terms, they will not be able to choose their trajectory correctly. The modern educational approach requires teachers to be open to diversity, ready for change, and possess innovative qualities. The new paradigm in teaching requires teachers to teach students to think independently, creatively, and critically, and these changes require teachers to create a new, flexible,

and tactful teaching style. The reason is that today, each student has their own speed, intensity, pace, and style of learning. Taking these aspects into account, it is advisable for teachers to use the most convenient and effective strategies for teaching English within the framework of an individual approach.

Didactics (educators) interpret the term "method" as a way of working for teachers and students aimed at acquiring knowledge, skills, abilities, forming a worldview in students, and creating opportunities for learning.¹ Jamol Jalalov's textbook "Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages" emphasizes that the term "method" has three main meanings. First, as a whole direction in the history of methodology;

Second, an education system that is part of the above direction;

Third, a method of interrelated activities between the teacher and the student

(methods of acquaintance, practice, and application). In the history of foreign language teaching, the first and second methods are usually referred to as "historical," and the third as "methods in the process of foreign language teaching."

When we talk about a method of teaching a foreign language, we mean a set of actions by the teacher and student that ensure the achievement of practical, general educational, educational, and developmental goals of foreign language teaching. The term "method" is used in the meanings of "a set of teaching methods" and "a direction of teaching." While the first meaning is used in teaching theory (e.g., methods of teaching oral speech, methods of teaching pronunciation), the second meaning is found in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, the translation method of foreign language teaching, the direct method, the conscious-comparative method, the traditional method, the intensive method, the audiovisual method, etc.²

Teaching is inseparable from learning. It cannot be defined in isolation. Teaching is the process of guiding and facilitating learning, helping students learn, and creating conditions for learning. A teacher's understanding of how students learn determines their educational philosophy, teaching style, approach, methods, and teaching techniques. If, for example, you view learning as a process of operant conditioning, as B. F. Skinner did, and believe that you need to develop a strict, step-by-step reinforcement program, then that is how you will teach. If learning a second language is viewed as a deductive (top-down) process, then the teacher will most likely prefer to present students with a set of rules and paradigms rather than allow them to "discover" the rules inductively (bottom-up).³

More than fifty years ago, Edward Anthony (1963) described the concept of "method" as the second link in a three-level hierarchy. He defined approach as a set of views on the nature of language, learning, and teaching. A method is defined as a general plan for the systematic presentation of a language course based on the chosen approach. Methods are specific activities used in the curriculum that are consistent with the method and, therefore, the approach.⁴

Edward Anthony's introduction of these three dimensions to English language teaching contributed to the development of all subjects, not just language acquisition. Approach, method, technique—these three basic concepts allow us to systematically structure any activity or process in a specific field. Their relationship is procedural and rigorous, ensuring practical application in education and research. Each level complements the previous one.

According to Edward Anthony, this hierarchically organized structure requires that the boundaries and functions of each level be determined by the level immediately below it. This approach is axiomatic, that is, self-evident and universally accepted. Methods, on the other hand, are procedural in nature, as they describe how a theoretical approach is applied through

the development of practical and concrete principles that can be applied in the classroom. Techniques are procedural in nature because they usually represent a limited number of learning steps that must be followed in the learning process.

An approach is the highest level of philosophy, decisions, or theoretical basis through which we understand and direct our actions in a particular area. The following approaches to foreign language teaching are widely promoted:

- The humanistic approach (emphasizes emotions and personal relationships with the teacher);
- Communicative approach (considers language primarily through communication);
- The behaviorist approach (implements language learning through repetition and phrases);
- Individual approach (a form of teaching that takes into account the unique characteristics, abilities, and interests of each student) and other approaches to language teaching.

A method is an intermediate level, representing a structured process or rule. It is designed to implement activities within the framework of an approach. A method is procedural in nature, translating theoretical rules into practical application, and also defines the goals, direction, activities, and roles of students. A method can also be called a "road map" or "blueprint." This previous one to the next. For example, in the humanistic approach – Community Language Learning (CLL) – mass language teaching, in the individual approach – it is advisable to use methods of conversation and interviews, observation, differentiated approach, and portfolios.

Methodology is the most specific and practical level, the specific actions or tools used in teaching or other activities. Methodologies must always correspond to the method. They represent the practical application of the method, the implementation of the established rules of the method. "Methodology implements the method, and the method is applied in accordance with the approach" (Anthony, 1963).

Indeed, if English teachers are unable to organize lessons effectively and impart language skills at the right time and in the right direction, there will be no positive changes in the quality of education. To be an effective teacher, it is extremely important for the student to fully understand the three concepts mentioned above in order to be able to transfer their knowledge and overcome difficulties in the learning process. At the same time, the ability to rank these three levels, systematically organize them, evaluate them, and see their prospects will give meaning to the lives of both students and teachers in the future. This is because these three levels require a systematic approach.

In conclusion, it can be noted that before developing language learning skills in students, teachers need to understand the essence and principles of these three concepts. In the context of the rapid development of an innovative teaching system, when the knowledge and experience required of students are becoming more complex in line with the demands of the times, our teachers are required to have pedagogical competencies and perform a number of duties. In this regard, we consider it appropriate to present the following recommendations and ideas.

First of all, a comprehensive explanation of the theory behind these three terms to students enrolled in higher education institutions, i.e., a systematic explanation of the practices currently implemented in secondary schools, will greatly contribute to the effectiveness of the education system by instilling a new perspective and enthusiasm in future teachers.

Second, the essence of the three terms mentioned above should be taught in greater depth in a module aimed at encouraging teachers to come up with new ideas and improve their innovative qualities while enhancing their professional teaching skills at professional development centers.

Thirdly, we believe that if the leaders and members of foreign language teachers' associations in schools regularly organize scientific seminars focused on the environment of their organization and the personal characteristics of their students, this will have a positive impact on the educational environment and effectiveness.

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